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Deliverable 6.1 Data Management Plan

V2.0

Project number: **101061233**
Project acronym: **RECHARGE**
Project name: **Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth and Engagement**
Funding call: **HORIZON-CL2-2021-HERITAGE-01-02**
Project starting date: **1 October 2022**
Project end date: **30 September 2025**
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Version: **2.0**
Date: **02 February 2026**
Dissemination level: **PU (Public)**

Overview of Changes

V2.0 Update M36

Version v2.0 is the final update of the Data Management Plan for the RECHARGE project. It includes the information about data publications and archiving of project data for long term preservation.

Location of Change	Description of Change
Section 2, table 2 data summary	Publication and archiving information updated per data package
Section 3, paragraph 3.2.1.	Link to RECHARGE Culture Community on Zenodo added; updated information on agreements with Zenodo
Section 3, paragraph 3.3	Updated information on data formats.
Section 3, paragraph 3.4.1.	Updated license for metadata
Section 3, paragraph 3.4.2	Updated information on the readme file.
Section 4	Updated information about other research outputs; DOI links included in table 5.
Section 6, paragraph 6.1	Added information about data storage and data archiving.
Closing Remarks	Updated information about development of the DMP throughout the project.

V1.2 Update M24

Version v1.2 includes changes following a reassessment and update of the DMP after M24. The changes and where they can be found are included in the table below.

Location of Change	Description of Change
Section 2, table 2 data summary	Updated information for T2.4 Running CH Living Labs
Section 3, paragraph 3.4.1 Licence	Adjusted guideline to submit work with CC-BY licence rather than CC0 licence following advice from EUR Data Steward.
Section 4 other research outputs	Updated section to include a table of other research outputs so far developed and made available online on the RECHARGE platform.

V1.1 Response to General Project Review Consolidated Report

Version v1.1 of the DMP (v1.1) includes the incorporation of recommendations following the review of periodic report 1 (M1-12) on 16 November 2023. The recommendations are listed below, followed by an explanation of how they were incorporated in the current DMP.

Recommendation	Actions to include in DMP v1.1
The Data Management plan draws on a template provided by the European Commission.	Format of the DMP has been adjusted to match RECHARGE project document formatting style.
However, it lacks information regarding the	Under section 6 Data Security, table 6 outlines data storage solutions and includes per solution the term of storage.

question “How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?” and this information needs to be added.	RECHARGE reusable data will be stored on Zenodo, where data will remain reusable at minimum 10 years after the end of the project and at maximum until the lifetime of the repository.
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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

Abstract

This document outlines the DMP prepared for the RECHARGE project. It informs about the intentions of the consortium partners concerning data collection, its documentation, sharing and short- and long-term storage. It represents the most up-to-date knowledge and awareness of research data management, as well as data collected in the scope of the RECHARGE project. The DMP evolved during the lifespan of the project and this is its last update.

About the RECHARGE Project

RECHARGE stands for Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth and Engagement, which are keywords that together synthesize the aim of the project itself: to reinvigorate community participation as added economic value for cultural heritage institutions across Europe.

Funded within the European Union's HORIZON Europe programme, the key funding programme for research and innovation within the EU, RECHARGE supports cultural heritage institutions in diversifying their funding through a replicable and sustainable participatory business model, to acquire the necessary tools for its future developments, both in the digital realm and onsite.

RECHARGE builds on new and existing communities, networks and relationships related to cultural heritage institutions, to engage them in participatory management through cultural heritage Living Labs. These Living Labs, developed collaboratively and open to professionals and the public, aim at testing and devising innovative ways to harness resources, to ensure the development of sustainable future business models, focused on the creation and integration of value within each institution, and in the sector at large.

Consortium

Partner organisation name	Acronym	Country
Erasmus University Rotterdam	EUR	NL

Centrum Cyfrowe	FCC	PL
Fundación Goteo	GOTEO	ES
Stichting Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid	NISV	NL
European Fashion Heritage Association	EFHA	IT
Creativity Lab	CLAB	EE
University of Valladolid	UVA	ES
Estonian Maritime Museum	EMM	EE
Textile Museum Prato	TMP	IT
The Hunt Museum	HUNT	IE

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1. Purpose of the Data Management Plan

The DMP aimed to provide a clear outline of the key principles and provisions regarding data within the scope of the project. In short, it specified what datasets RECHARGE were generated or re-used, how these were exploited and made available for reuse, and how the datasets were curated and archived. The RECHARGE DMP also described how the research data within the project met FAIR guiding principles to become findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

This document drew on the [template provided by the European commission](#). The first section of the DMP summarised the relevant datasets within the RECHARGE project, and it was followed by FAIR data provisions and allocation of resources. In addition, the document covered aspects of data security, ethics, and GDPR compliance.

Table 1: Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	15/03/2023	Internal review version	Joanna Mania, Ilaria Rosetti
v0.2	15/03/2023 - 23/03/2023	Revision	Úna Hussey, Marta Franceschini, Simon Thompson, Trilce Navarrete
v0.3	28/03/2023	Revision	Gai Umali, Chiara Stenico
V1.0	31/03/2023	Submission version	Joanna Mania, Ilaria Rosetti
V1.1	10/01/2024	Resubmission version	Joanna Mania, Ilaria Rosetti, Emma de Mooij
V1.2	-	Resubmission version	Joanna Mania, Úna Hussey, Emma de Mooij
V2.0	03/12/2025	Revision	Joanna Mania, Emma de Mooij

2. Data summary

A general overview of the data collected, published and archived in the RECHARGE is presented in Table 2: *Data Summary*.

Table 2: Data Summary

WP	Type	Formats	Considerations	Size	Origin	Data Access
1	T1.1 Analysis of the Current Participatory Management and Participatory Business Models in Cultural Heritage Sector and Beyond					
	Desk research: Cultural living labs https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17590699 (open access) EUR Archive: Desk research - multiple versions of the spreadsheet.					
	T1.2 Motivation for Participation EUR Archive: documents, transcripts and raw data.					
T1.3 Value of Participation						

	<p>Data package: Value of participation by Museum Communities https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17412939</p> <p>EUR Archive: raw data, research materials, codebook.</p>
	<p>T1.4 Forging Impactful and Durable Partnerships and Collaborations</p> <p>Data package: Interviews - Forging Impactful and Durable Partnerships and Collaborations https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751189 (restricted access)</p> <p>EUR Archive: processed data, signed informed consent, research materials, codebook, templates.</p>
2	<p>T2.1 Network Engagement</p> <p>EUR Archive: stakeholder mapping and stakeholder engagement documentation.</p>
	<p>T2.2 Co-creating the RECHARGE models</p> <p>EUR Archive: documentation of Business Models canvas iterations, links to recorded co-creation sessions and Miro boards.</p>
	<p>T2.3 Setting up the Living Labs</p> <p>EUR Archive: documentation on Next Living Labs, including proposal, application stats, onboarding videos.</p>
	<p>T2.4 Running the CH Living Lab</p> <p>EUR Archive: interview transcriptions, meeting recordings, informed consent forms, images, reports, documentation, mentorship materials.</p>
	<p>T2.5 Analysis of the Prototypes</p> <p>EUR Archive: report, documentation of reflections.</p>
3	<p>T3.1 Effectiveness of Participatory Operational Strategies</p> <p>Data package: Value of participation by Stakeholders https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434093 (open access)</p> <p>EUR Archive: survey (raw and processed), dictionary.</p>
	<p>T3.2 Measuring Resilience</p> <p>Data summary: Resilience in the CHIs - Cultural Volunteering as Catalyst for Participatory Practices https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17791906 (open access)</p> <p>EUR Archive: raw transcripts, readme, research materials.</p>
	<p>T3.3 Viability and Value Creation Capacity</p> <p>Data package: Models of Cooperation between Artistic Workers and Cultural Organizations https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17359164 (open access)</p> <p>EUR Archive: processed data, authorization form, codebook.</p> <p>Data package: TBD</p>

	EUR Archive: raw survey data, analysis.
	T3.4 Indicators of Participation
	EUR Archive: raw data, impact assessment tracking document, KPIs structure, presentation.
4	T4.1 Recharge Playbook
	EUR Archive: documentation of the process and content creation, workshops.
	T4.2 RECHARGE Academy
	EUR Archive: drawings, presentation, assessment, booklet, rules of participation, timeline.
	T4.3 Knowledge Base
	EUR Archive: educational videos, stories, video testimonials, presentation, documentation on preparation, brainstorming, planning, learning objectives, etc.
	T4.4 Framework for transferability
	EUR Archive: Recaps of webinars, pamphlets, other documentation.
6	Project Management
	EUR Archive: - Conference Presentations

Origin: R – reuse, G – generate, *Data Access:* O – Open, R – Restricted, TBU – to be updated, NA – not applicable, A/A – as above

3. FAIR Data

FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. It is a framework for thinking about, preparing and sharing data in a way to maximize its use (and reuse). Findable refers to discovery of datasets, which is achieved through registering them in secure data repositories together with metadata (description of the data) and persistent identifiers (a unique, long-term link). Accessible means that both humans and computers should gain access to the (meta)data, and when appropriate, under specified restrictions and/or defined access protocols. Research data should be set to be easily combined with other datasets, meaning interoperable. Lastly, preparing data for re-use in a future requires making it self-evident and replicable by including transparent documentation and re-use license.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Persistent Identifier: DOI

Datasets, research materials and research outputs are assigned DOI via Zenodo. It is an obligatory element of every record. DOIs of the datasets and related publications are included in the accompanying metadata.

3.1.2 Metadata schema: Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)

Zenodo follows the DCMI metadata standard. Next to indexing published records in its own search engine, Zenodo sends and indexes metadata in the DataCite servers, links data to OpenAIRE Explore..

A set of keywords were selected for consistency and to optimize the discoverability and re-usage of the (meta)data.

Table 3: List of metadata

Name of metadata standard	Description
1. Title (M)	A name given to the resource.
2. Creator (M)	An entity responsible for making the resource.
3. Subject (MA)	A topic of the resource.
4. Description (MA)	Description may include but is not limited to: an abstract, a table of contents, a graphical representation, or a free-text account of the resource.
5. Publisher (MA)	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6. Contributor (R)	An entity responsible for making contributions to the resource.
7. Date (M)	Recommended practice is to express the date, date/time, or period of time according to ISO 8601-1 (YYYY-MM-YY)
8. Type (M)/(R)	The nature or genre of the resource.
9. Format (R)	The file format, physical medium, or dimensions of the resource.
10. Identifier (M)	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context, for example DOI.
11. Source (R)	A related resource from which the described resource is derived.
12. Language (R)	A language of the resource.
13. Relation (R)	A related resource.
14. Coverage (O)	Spatial topic and spatial applicability may be a named place or a location specified by its geographic coordinates.
15. Rights (R)	Access Rights may include information regarding access or restrictions based on privacy, security, or other policies.

M – Mandatory, MA – Mandatory when applicable, R – Recommended, O – Optional

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repository: Zenodo

RECHARGE deposited metadata and data in Zenodo, an open, general-purpose repository created under the OpenAIRE programme. All records were attached to the 'RECHARGE Culture community' (<https://zenodo.org/communities/recharge-culture/>). Metadata and record identifiers could be harvested via OAI-PMH and REST API.

For the purpose of the RECHARGE project, the consortium has not entered into additional agreements with Zenodo, except agreeing to the Terms of Use.

3.2.2 Accessibility of datasets

Where appropriate, RECHARGE consortium partners made datasets and other project outputs accessible for third parties for re-use on Zenodo. The openness of data depended greatly on the type of data classification. Non-personal data and materials were published open access. For data containing personal information the rule was as follows. If the balance between pseudonymization/anonymization of qualitative

data and data quality can be achieved, the consortium partners will consider making them open access for re-use. If not, the qualitative data was published under restricted access, and metadata included information about how and under what condition to access data. Special considerations were given to community participants, if they are of a vulnerable nature or classified as minor. None of the research outputs have been embargoed. .

The project did not see the need to establish a data access committee. For data packages published with restricted access, a data access protocol provides instructions to third parties if and how they may gain access to the complete data package..

3.2.3 Accessibility of metadata

The access to the metadata is public, and no authorization is required to retrieve it. According to the Zenodo FAIR Principles, metadata is stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which is separate from the data itself. Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least.

When necessary, information about software (and their versions) needed to open, process or analyze data were included in the dataset documentation.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The research datasets, metadata and documentation were as much as possible compliant with best standards for interoperability and re-use.

Description of the datasets and metadata are in English to increase their discoverability and accessibility. While not all datasets have been converted to open formats, they are saved in commonly used data formats (.docx, .xlsx). The relation between resources can be made through the “Relation” element in the metadata. While uploading data to the repository, consistent keywords were used.

In terms of interoperable metadata, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as an internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 Licence

RECHARGE data, materials, playbooks, workflows, protocols, etc are of interest to cultural heritage institutions and researchers in the field of heritage studies, cultural economics, entrepreneurship and innovation, among others.

Striving for a greater impact of the RECHARGE project, better reproducibility, transparency and possibility for rigorous peer-review process, research data (non-personal) and other research outputs, are labelled with Creative Commons CC-BY licence. This licence allows reusers to distribute, adapt, remix and build upon the research outputs as long as the credits are given to the authors, including commercial use. Metadata are licensed as CC0.

3.4.2 Project-level documentation

Datasets published on Zenodo contain a descriptive README file. The example README file was included in the SURF Research Drive folder for each WP (file: *README-template.txt*). The template contained the following information:

- title of the project/dataset

- motivation for data collection
- research question
- a brief description of the contents of each file or group of files
- contract information
- methodology
- tools used for data collection
- dates of data collection
- software used for data processing and/ or analysis
- the provenance of the data and any prior processing (if re-using data)
- licence under which the data can be reused, of the access level placed on the data

3.4.3 Naming and versioning

Each WP was free to create their own system following the best practices listed below. The same list was included in the SURF Research Drive folder for each WP (file: *naming-and-versioning.txt*).

- Avoid spaces, punctuation, case sensitivity and special characters
- Deliberate use of delimiters. For example, a hyphen (-) to mean “different words that are part of the same chunk”, and underscore (_) to separate different chunks of metadata
- Choose keywords and file names that are sufficiently descriptive,
- Use YYYY-MM-DD date format (ISO 8601 standard)
- To order files put date or number first
- Include the version of the file
- Create a version control table that lists the number of changes, date, and their purpose
- Add sequential numbers at the end of the file name (for example: *_v1*, *_v2*)
- Record the date in the file naming

Figure 1: Example of folder organisation

3.4.4 Data quality assurance

The consortium partners had ambition to produce reliable data that yield reproducible research results. To promote quality assurance throughout the project, following steps could be taken:

Table 4: Data quality assurance

Research phase	Measures
Data collection (literature review, interviews, focus groups, and workshops)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Precise record of audio and visual samples and notes, and authenticity of secondary material - Use of protocols for the analysis of secondary databases, and for interviews, surveys, focus groups, and workshops - Quality of collected sound, video, and images - Participant consent to use the recordings, transcriptions, notes, and other outputs to the fullest - Data is curated in a way that information not allowed by consent or not relevant to research question is excluded from analysis
Digitalization and data entry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of templates for documentations - Purposeful folder structure to organise data files - Notes and documentation about data
Data checking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correct errors made during transcription - Check data completeness - Detect errors and anomalous values - Compare notes
Data authenticity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keep and maintain original data file - Keep history of data analysis files

4. Other research outputs

Other research outputs generated during the RECHARGE project (for example: workflows, protocols, workshop materials, etc.) will be considered for management and handled according to FAIR principles. Other research output that was immediately appropriate for open access sharing is presented on the RECHARGE platform as part of the Knowledge Base and on Zenodo. Table 5 presents an overview of, specifically, other research output developed by the project.

Additionally, RECHARGE has developed a wealth of tools and resources beyond its formal deliverables and scientific publications, all of which are available on the RECHARGE Knowledge Base (<https://recharge-culture.eu/processes/knowledge-base>). To ensure that the results of the project have a wide reach in the communities of cultural and creative professionals, all RECHARGE resources are also available on a dedicated project page on the Heritage Research Hub (<https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/project/recharge/>).

Table 5: RECHARGE Other Research Output

WP	Title of research output	DOI
Research reports		
1	Typology of Participatory Practices in the Cultural Heritage Sector	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242559

1	Allocating Value to Participatory Dimensions and Strategies by Museum Communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242864
3	Models of Cooperation between Creatives and Museums	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17359281
Presentations (scholarly and professional)		
1	Living Labs as Catalysts of Participatory Business Models for Cultural Heritage Institutions: A Literature Review	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205764
1	D1.1 Models	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17193625
1	Exploring the Theoretical Foundations of Participatory Practices	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17192214
1	RECHARGE Application of the Four Phases of Participatory Business Models in Heritage	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259788
2	Tapping into Corporate Social Responsibility – Developing Participatory Business Models to Tackle Urban Challenges with Communities and Corporates	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205811
2	RECHARGE: Participatory Cultural Business Models	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14245832
2 & 3	Co-Creating a Sustainable Future	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205887
2 & 4	RECHARGING Business Models. Strengthening Cultural Heritage Organizations through Living Labs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17709760
3	Value of Participation – The RECHARGE Perspective	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205915
3	European Projects on Participation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152277
3	Volunteering in Cultural Institutions and Commons-Oriented Organizations: Navigating the Gap Between Policy and Practice	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17192135
4	Working Together for Cultural Heritage – RECHARGE Recommendations for Sustainable Collaboration	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063069
n/a	What is RECHARGE? Capturing Value through Participatory Innovation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17650438
n/a	RECHARGE – Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth and Engagement	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17193789
n/a	The Value of Participation – RECHARGE	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17193730
Posters		
4	Working Together for Cultural Heritage – RECHARGE Recommendations for Sustainable Collaboration	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063069

n/a	RECHARGE – Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth and Engagement	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163978
Other		
n/a	RECHARGE Keywords	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14261328
4	Playbook V1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14261368
4	Playbook V2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164061
4	Enhancing Participatory Approaches in Cultural Heritage Organisations for a more Sustainable and Inclusive Sector	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063177
4	Enhancing Participatory Approaches in Cultural Heritage Organisations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063217
5	RECHARGE Performance Monitor	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17749238

5. Allocation of resources

5.1 FAIR data preparation

The responsibility for implementing FAIR practices laid on all RECHARGE partners collecting research data, if needed with help of a data steward. It required foremost time investment to ensure data quality as well as preparation of (pseudonymized) transcripts, data documentation, project organization, format files into sustainable formats, and digitalization of paper materials. There were no extra costs needed to cover those.

5.2 Infrastructure

Information about the costs of infrastructure are included in Table 6: *Specifications of data storage solution*.

5.3 Expertise

The implementation of the best RDM practices and FAIR principles was supported by professional expertise of data stewards, privacy officers, and legal advisors available through project coordinator.

6. Data security

6.1 Secure storage infrastructure

RECHARGE project made use of several cloud storage solutions throughout the project. Consortium partners could decide to temporarily store research data using their own infrastructure. EUR Research Drive was set to be accessible to each of them to use as primarily storage or as a back-up.

Data transfer/exchange between the project partners took place via EUR Research Drive or using secure data transfer service SURFfilesender. That process was regulated by a separate data sharing agreement in the consortium (see also 7.1. *GDPR Compliance*).

Upon completion of the project, data stored in the SURF Research Drive was transferred to EUR Archive (EUR Yoda Vault) in two batches, on 17.12.2025 and 22.01.2026. Creator is set to ESHCC Data Steward, who facilitated the transfer of data between the storage solution. The responsibility for the content of archival packages lies with RECHARGE partners directly. For each work package (except WP5), a

separate workspace has been created and assigned to the Principal Investigator (see Picture 2). Metadata for each WP has been added, including a description of each WP. The folder structure is preserved.

The SURF Research Drive will be permanently deleted. RECHARGE partners will be informed about it and provided information on how to access the EUR Yoda Vault (direct access or via contact with ESHCC Data Steward).

Figure 2: Workspace organization in EUR Archive.

research-recharge-wp1-sustainable-financing-participatory-pract	
research-recharge-wp2-ch-living-labs	
research-recharge-wp3-models-assessment-indicators	
research-recharge-wp4-capacity-building-transferability	
research-recharge-wp6-project-management	

Table 6: Specifications of data storage solution

Storage solution	Stored data	Controlled Data Access	Costs	Preservation period	Security assessment
Google Drive for Education Plus	Administrative data and documentation of project	All consortium members	Free of charge, provided by EUR	Short-term: duration of the project. Transferred at the end of the project to EUR Data Archive	Approved to be used for internal data, including personal data
EUR Research SURFdrive	Research datasets, signed informed consent forms	Consortium researchers	Free up to 500GB, provided by EUR	Short-term: duration of the project. Transferred at the end of the project to EUR Data Archive.	Assessed and approved to be used for research data, including special categories of personal data.
Zenodo	Research data, metadata, research, materials and other outputs	Public	Free of charge	Long-term: min. 10 years after completion of the project, max. lifetime of repository	Information about security can be found here: https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/
EUR Data Archive	Project documentation, research data, metadata, other outputs	To be updated	Free up to 500GB, provided by EUR	Long-term: 10 years after completion of the project*	Assessed and approved to be used for research data, including special categories of personal data and sensitive data

*The archive duration will be 10 years after either the assignment of a persistent identifier or the publication of a related work following the project completion, whichever is later. The decision about deletion or destruction will be carried out only after considering all legal and ethical perspectives, as well as confidentiality and security aspects. The considerations also include the interests of funders, stakeholders,

consortium partners and employees. The rationale for deletion or destruction of research data should be explained in the updated metadata file.

7. Ethics

To ensure that all ethical requirements are met, the project coordination team sought official approval from the independent Research Ethics Review Committee at EUR. The ethics review procedure at EUR was in line with the general standards of the (social) sciences and the humanities, detailed in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for research integrity (2018), and substantiated in the EUR ethics review policy. Ethical clearance (ETH2223-0301) was conditionally provided by the ESHCC Research Ethics Review Committee at EUR on 30-01-2023 for a period of three years, under the commitment to submit periodical amendments, as relevant.

In addition, an external, independent Ethics Advisor was appointed to serve as a consultant on ethical issues during the project, available to each Consortium partner.

8. GDPR compliance

The Consortium was guided by the principle of data minimisation when collecting data. This means that only data that was strictly necessary to answer the research question had been collected.

The processing of data involved in this research was not likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the participants, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purpose of the processing of research data. This finding was the result of a Data Protection Impact Assessment conducted over the research where it was identified that the risk impact upon interviewees was minimal. To ensure that the identified risks were continually addressed, technological and organizational measures and arrangements have been set in place.

The research questions did not require the collection of sensitive data. For instance:

- The participatory online RECHARGE platform was used to register to the different online and offline project activities:
 - Only the chosen nickname of the platform's users were visible (no email, no personal information)
 - The contact details (name, surname, email, profession) of the participants in the focus groups were gathered for registration purposes and safely stored by the living labs but were not used for the analysis. Only anonymized/pseudonymized data was used, as it was detailed in the consent form. When the sessions were recorded, the contributions were anonymized/pseudonymized in the transcript, as it was detailed in the consent form.
 - The contact details (email, maybe age, and profession) of the participants in the survey were gathered, but only anonymized/pseudonymized information will be used in the analysis, as it was detailed in the consent form.
- The interviews with cultural heritage institutions were analyzed with no personal reference to the interviewee unless prior consent was provided through a detailed consent form.

Research participants/interviewees participate voluntarily as was evidenced by their written or digitally provided consent. The informed consent provided information about the goals of the research, what data was collected and how, and what would happen during the research. Also, they made clear what and how data was published, and on what terms. Participants were advised about their data subject rights under the GDPR and provided with the contact details of the respective party's Data Protection Officer and the appropriate national Data Protection Authority if they had data privacy related questions or complaints.

EUR provided informed consent templates that could be tailored to a specific audience and data collection

and help unify standards across partners. Moreover, some partners translated the informed consent form into the participants' mother tongue. If needed, the participants had the opportunity to read what was published before publication, to verify their consent.

While it was not the aim to collect any sensitive or special category information, this could occur unintentionally. If the sensitive information was relevant to the research question and kept (in any shape or form), the consortium partners were responsible for storing it safely by, for instance, using storing tool with additional security measures, restricted access, encryption, VPN. If the information was irrelevant to the research questions, it was deleted, removed or omitted (for example, in transcriptions).

Raw research data was pseudonymized or anonymized. Research data was managed and stored in an environment that was individually managed by the respective parties in accordance with procedures for responsible data management and in consultation with the data stewards.

A Joint Controllership Agreement (JCA) governed the roles and relationships among the parties to the Consortium pursuant to Article 26 GDPR. The JCA outlined in a transparent manner the respective responsibilities of the parties under the GDPR. In particular, the JCA provided arrangements in regard to actions to be taken when interviewees exercise their data subject rights.

Participants interacting with RECHARGE participatory platforms adhered to its Terms and Conditions of use. Information registered for the registration purposes as well as information needed for proper website functioning was kept confidential and will not be re-used for any purpose.

Any privacy risk during the project were consulted with EUR Privacy Officer to help reduce, mitigate, or remove them.

9. Other issues

The consortium members did not make use of other data management procedures than those outlined in this document.

Closing remarks

This document has outlined data management strategy and information for the RECHARGE project. At month 36, the date of project closure, many datasets, outputs and reports related to the project have been published on RECHARGE Culture Community on Zenodo. The remaining ones will be published upon acceptance by the European Commission. The archiving process started after the official project period had ended.